

**DIABETES CARE IN PUBLIC HEALTH FACILITIES IN INDIA- A
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ABSTRACT

Diabetes Mellitus (Type 2) is a chronic metabolic disease which is observed to be highly widespread gradually everywhere in the world. Because of the increase in the middle age people to ageing, the effect of Diabetes Mellitus TYPE 2 is expected to become an epidemic in the next decade. This review is based on a search of Medline, goggle scholar and citation lists of relevant publications. Screening and diagnosis is based on American diabetes association Criteria. There may be no cure for the disease but treatment is provided to avoid risk of further complications such as diabetic cardiomyopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy. The treatment modifications such as good healthy life style, take precautions for obesity, OHAs and insulin sensitizers can provide a healthy outcome. A general habit of training exercises can help improve and control glycemic levels, further preventing a

complicating outcome. The medications used in therapy of type 2 Diabetes Mellitus are met form in, a biguanide that reduces insulin resistance, is the highly prescribed first line medication Other effective medications include sulfonylurea's, thiazolidinediones, GLP-1 agonists, SGLT- 2 inhibitors and glinides. The study suggests that the increasing levels of General Random Blood Sugar and the increasing age further increases the risk of various complications associated with type2 Diabetes Mellitus.

KEYWORDS: Diabetes- Type 2, Diabetes Mellitus, Effects, and Treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes, a major non-communicable disease has been a problem of both developing and non-developing countries.^[1-3] Long standing uncontrolled diabetes is known to cause microvascular and macrovascular complications affecting the major organs like eyes, kidney and brain along with the cardiovascular complications like hypertension and dyslipidemia.^[4] that may lead to complications in these individuals.

Lack of awareness on the importance of glycaemic control, importance of adherence to medications, financial constraints or self-negligence could be the common causes that may lead to complications in these individuals. Similarly, the uncontrolled glycaemic state on a long run results into the development of co morbid conditions which further worsen the health state and adds to the expense in health management.^[4-8]

Several research and review studies have been performed to evaluate the prevalence and the drug utilized in the management of type 2 diabetes. Further, studies have been conducted to provide useful insights into the present prescribing trends, rational and irrational medications.^[5,9-11] such studies can help us to compare the treating strategies available in this common condition and to prepare standard treatment guidelines to treat and prevent the related complication of diabetes. Irrational use of medicines remains a major concern in practice applicable to diabetes as well, where patients are invariably suffering with comorbid conditions requiring more than one medication thus landing in to practice of polypharmacy.

Similarly, with the compromised immunity, the diabetic individuals who are more prone for infections succumb to the antibiotic resistance and adverse effects in cases where irrational or inappropriate antimicrobials are used, thus resulting into economic burden in their health management.^[5] Such situations further contribute to non-adherence of medications and worsen the diabetic control. Hence, the study has been taken up to evaluate the drug pattern or the prescription pattern in patients of type 2 diabetes with associated complications.

Diabetes Mellitus and its complications

Diabetes Mellitus is a chronic metabolic non-communicable disease characterised by high blood glucose levels that lead to health defects in the body's ability to produce insulin. When we eat food, the pancreas releases insulin. Insulin allows sugar to move from the blood into

the cells. Sugar levels in the blood rise when the body's cells do not use insulin effectively or when the body is unable to produce enough insulin. The condition is primarily defined by elevated glucose levels (hyperglycemia), which causes microvascular damage such as retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy. Diabetes mellitus occurs when the body is unable to use glucose for energy due to insufficient amounts or loss of sensitivity to the hormone insulin. When the amount of glucose in the blood rises, as it does after a meal, the pancreas releases the hormone insulin. Insulin stimulates muscle and fat cells to remove glucose from the blood and the liver to metabolise glucose, resulting in normal blood sugar levels. Blood sugar levels in diabetics remain elevated. This could be because insulin is not produced at all, is not produced in sufficient quantities, or is not as effective as it should be. Type 1 diabetes (5%), an autoimmune disorder, and type 2 diabetes (95%), which is associated with obesity. Humans consume food, not glucose. As part of the normal digestion process, human foods are converted into glucose. Glucose enters the bloodstream after being converted, raising the level of dissolved glucose in the blood. The dissolved glucose is then carried by the bloodstream to the body's various tissues and cells. In 2017, diabetes alone exhausted about 5-25% share of an average Indian household earnings by spending about 31 billion US dollars management.^[12]

Some of the government and/or private organizations have tried to implement effective educational programs for increasing awareness about the proper management of diabetes.^[13]

The different promising approaches, attention and extemporization of efforts are essential for developing a strong healthcare system that delivers quality diabetes care of patients. Delivering accessible, affordable, and high-quality care are some of the major challenges it faces and therefore healthcare delivery systems must identify more proactive ways to manage patients in the community and in their homes. Jothydev's Professional Education Forum (JPEF) Annual Diabetes Convention is an international diabetes convention with the global participation of diabetes care professionals from all streams. JPEF Global Convention 2019 organized a discussion forum including diabetes experts from India who are actively involved in patient care either in clinical practice or in diabetes administration. The experts proposed a "White paper model" to sort out the challenges faced during diabetes management in India.

The article aims to explain how various manner of diabetes care can be collected to develop a awareness which will produce the development of the most appropriate health care system for India.

Diabetes database in India

International diabetes federation reveals that till 2021 about 75 million people were survived with diabetes and it will increase 93 million till 2030 in India. Out of 75 million, 53.1 million people with undiagnosed diabetes percentage.

A study conducted by Anjana et al in 15 states of India reported that the mean prevalence of prediabetes in India is 10.3% (state-wise range, 6.0–14.7%)^[14,15] Survey studies revealed that about 10–16% of the urban and 5–8% of the rural populations have diabetes.^[16, 17]

The Data in ICMR-INDIAB study reveals that the prevalence of undiagnosed hypertension, and dyslipidemia is high and the level of glycemic control among subjects with self-reported diabetes in India is poor.^[18,19,20]

Method

The study was carried out in a private Gomti hospital, Sultanpur Up, a 500-bed hospital that provides secondary healthcare and people from various parts of Sultanpur after obtaining the approval from Institutional Ethic committee. A total of 400 in-patients and 400 out-patients are treated and admitted on a daily basis in Gomti Hospital Sultanpur UP.

Another part of study was carried out in 200 diabetic patients with presence of other complications and admitted in medicine wards of Gomti hospital Sultanpur UP.

The hospital has several departments and wards, including cardiology, neurology, intensive care units, and medical and surgical wards.

Objectives

The study aims to reach out to people who have type 2 diabetes mellitus and raise awareness about its complications. In terms of blood glucose control, this prevents many other Diabetes mellitus complications and life-threatening complications and Health hazards.

Study design

The Importance of Diabetes Management and Complication Prevention.

Size of type 1. This study contains data from 2,000 patients. 3. To investigate patient drug responses. 4. To investigate the various complications associated with type 2 diabetes.

Study materials: Patient case sheets, Medical records, Patient review of chief complaints, illness history, social history, and lifestyle.

Procedure for study

A specially designed data collection form was used to collect data and the data was analyzed using Statistics.

Study Population and Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Another part of the study was carried out in 200 diabetic patients with presence of other complications and admitted in medicine wards of Gomti hospital Sultanpur UP.

Inclusion criteria

- The patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes with presence of other complications
- The patients aged above 18 years
- The patients who are willing to sign the written consent form

Exclusion Criteria

- The patients having only type 2 diabetes with no complications
- Patients below 18 years of age
- The patients who are not willing to sign the written consent form

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first part of this study was carried out with 2000 patients; out of them 743 (37%) were male patients and 956 (48%) were female patients.

Demographical study

Table 1: Gender Distribution.

Gender	No of Patients
Male	743
Female	956

Discussion- Gender distribution is represented in the table above. Out of a sample size of 2,000, 743 members belonged to the male category, while 956 members belonged to the female category. The information was obtained from the Gomti Hospital in Sultanpur, Uttar Pradesh. Table 1 summarises the findings of the study. Figure-1 the mean S.D. was discovered to be 849 ± 106.5 .

Table 2: Age and Gender Distribution.

AGE	MALE	FEMALE
20-30	42	47
30-40	56	72
40-50	136	154
50-60	246	327
60-70	178	239
70-80	142	159

Discussion:- The age distribution in this study reveals that the age group of 15-19 the age group of 20-30,42 members belong to male, 47 members belong to female category, the age group of 30-40,56 members belong to male and 72 members belong to female category, the age group of 40-50,136 members belong to male and 154 members belong to female category, the age group of 50-60,246 members belong to male and 327 members belong to female category¹ It was presented in Table no 2 and Figure no 2 The Mean \pm S.D was found to be 133 ± 76 and 166 ± 104 .

Bar diagram age and gender distribution

Table 3: The rate of appearance of no.of patients receiving dual therapy.

GRBS	No of Patients treated with dual therapy
150-200	175
200-250	146
250-300	41
300-350	24
350-400	00

Discussion-- In this study, GBRS ranged between 150 and 200, with a total of 175 patients receiving dual therapy. GBRS ranged between 350 and 400, with no patients receiving treatment. GBRS ranged from 200 to 250, and 146 patients were treated with dual therapy. GBRS ranged from 250 to 300, and 41 patients received dual therapy. GBRS ranged from 300 to 350, and 24 patients received dual therapy. The mean standard deviation was found to be 77 ± 78 .

Table 4: The rate of appearance of patients receiving triple therapy.

GRBS	No of Patients treated with dual therapy
150-200	45
200-250	61
250-300	114
300-350	147
350-400	169

Discussion- According to this table, more triple therapy was administered in the GBRS range of 350-400, while less triple therapy was administered in the GBRS range of 150-200. The mean S.D. was determined to be 107 ± 53 . It was shown in Table No. 4 and Figure No. 4.

In another part of study in which 200 admitted patients in medicine ward, 20 (10%) having the 50-60 kg of body weight, 126 (52%) in range of 61-70 kg of body weight, 72 (36%) having the body weight of 72-80 kg while only 4(2%) were in range of 82-90 kg of body weight. All the patients were diabetic with past history. In all the patients, 116 patients were diabetes in the time limit of 5 years, 74 patients were diabetic more than 5 years and less than 10 years while 10 patients had the symptoms of diabetes more than 10 years.

Authors found that 160 (80%) patients were regularly taking the medicines for treatment of diabetes, while 18(9%) patients were irregular routine of having medicine of diabetes and 22 (11%) were not aware about their symptoms of diabetes and medications, 106 patients had medication of metformin, 62 patients had medication of metformin in combination of glimepride, Saxagliptin, Alpha-glucosidase inhibitor and Pioglitazone while 30 were on the medication of Insulin Preparation. Authors found that 106 (53%) of diabetic patients were having the precautions by diet control while 64 (37%) were not aware of diet control or any precaution regarding their diet control.

The patients admitted in the medical wards of Gomti hospital were associated with other medical conditions like kidney disease, heart disease, Urinary tract disease, liver disease and neuro diseases (Table 5 and Figure 5).

In this procedure out of all the 200 patients admitted in the medicine wards 45% were treated with insulin in addition to the oral preparations of diabetic treatment, 35% treated only with oral preparations of diabetic treatment and 20% were only treated with insulin (Figure 6). Most of the diabetic patients were treated with Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor (52%), 24% patients were treated with biaguanides, 12% patients were treated with sulphonyl urea, 4% patients were treated with Thiazolidinedione while remaining 2% patients were treated with Alpha-glucosidase inhibitor and 6% patients with GLP-1 receptor agonist.

Among 200 patients who treated with insulin, it was noticed that most commonly prescribed insulin was short acting insulin (45%), another patients treated with rapid acting insulin (12%), another patients treated with intermediate acting insulin (5%) and long acting insulin (5%).

Table 5: Diagnosis of the patients admitted in Medicine ward of Gomti Hospital, Sultanpur.

S. No.	Diagnosis of the patients admitted in Medicine ward	Number
1	Urinary tract infections, Hypertension	87
2	Diabetic Kindney Disease	56
3	Diabetes and stroke	44
4	Diabetic retinopathy	43
5	Diabetic neuropathy	38
6	Glucoma	32
7	Cataract	30
8	Diabetic foot	28
9	Arteriosclerosis	14

Figure 1: Gender Distribution.

Figure 2: Age and Gender distribution bar diagram.

Figure 3: Bar diagram representing no.of patients receiving dual therapy.

Figure 4: Pie chart representing no.of patients receiving triple Therapy.

Figure 5: Pie chart representing Diabetic patients with different disorders.

Figure 6: Pie chart representing Diabetic patients with different type of Insulin treatments.

CONCLUSION

Poor diabetes management has an impact on diabetic complications, lower medication adherence, and a negative impact on patients' socioeconomic status. This can be avoided through patient counselling or patient education during diabetes management. All above data indicates that patients find the best treatment with rapid acting are less as comparison to Patients with oral treatments. Therefore, it is essential to have proper treatment guidelines along with regular counselling to the diabetic patients pertaining to the importance of adherence to medications and patients compliance that can refrain them from long standing complications and lessening with their economic burdens.

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